

Exploring Language Learning Strategy Use in Afghanistan: A Gender-Based Analysis

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Abstract

This research analyzed how Afghan EFL learners vary in or align with language learning strategies (LLS) by gender. The study addressed 140 undergraduate students majoring in English language and literature at Parwan University, distributed equally between 70 male and 70 female participants. Data were obtained using two tools: a demographic survey and Oxford's Strategy Inventory for Language Learning (SILL). An independent samples t-test was implemented to compare the average strategy use of male and female students in terms of their inclinations and adoption of LLS. The results revealed that Afghan EFL students are moderately engaged in language learning strategies. Across the different categories, compensation and metacognitive strategies were used predominantly. On the other hand, cognitive and memory strategies were less commonly adopted among Afghan EFL learners. Furthermore, quantitative analysis indicated no meaningful gender-based contrasts in the overall implementation of LLS.

Keywords: *Afghanistan, EFL learners, gender, Language learning strategies, SILL.*

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Introduction

Since language learning and teaching methods have shifted from a teacher-centered to a student-centered approach, language practitioners have attempted to render a pattern on how individual learners come to learn a language independently. Initially, studies by Naiman, Neil, Frohlich, Hans, Stem, and Todesco addressed the field of LLS in 1978, and the primary focus was on the characteristics of a "good language learner". The first attempts, particularly the use of LLS by EFL learners and the relationship between their affecting factors (e.g., age, gender, proficiency level, and self-efficacy), became the main domains of research in this field. Primarily, researchers would like to

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differentiate between “good” and “poor” EFL learners. (See Naiman et al., 1978; Rubin, 1975). Consequently, many researchers tried to identify the employment of LLS by language learners and found out that more proficient learners adopt further strategies than less proficient language learners (Tabeti, 2019; Habók & Magyar, 2018; Alfian, 2018; Ghavamnia, Kassaian, & Dabaghi, 2011; Green & Oxford, 1995).

In the 1970s, the purpose of many studies was to determine the behaviors, attitudes, and thoughts of ‘good language learners’, so the researchers were interested in discovering the strategies adopted by proficient language learners in comparison to low-proficiency language learners. Thereafter, in the 1980s, as Kamalizad & Kalilzadeh (2016) stated, attention was drawn to the factors affecting language learners’ strategy use and the effect size. As a result, numerous lists and language learning strategy inventories have been devised (e.g., O’Malley & Chamot, 1995; Wenden, 1991; Oxford, 1990) to determine what processes, behaviors, and attitudes are applied by language learners that facilitate language acquisition, storage, and retrieval of information (Weinstein & Mayer, 1986). Among them, Oxford’s Strategy Inventory for Language Learning (SILL) has captured researchers’ attention and is the most updated and comprehensive inventory list. This so-called inventory list primarily labels LLS into two (direct and indirect strategies). Furthermore, the direct category is sub-grouped into memory, cognitive, and compensation strategies, and the indirect strategy is sub-categorized into metacognitive, affective, and social strategies. Overall, the questionnaire for the Strategy Inventory for (SILL) consists of 50 Likert-scale questions (Riazi & Rahimi, 2005).

LLS use can be influenced by many different variables, such as the language being learned, learning stage, awareness degree, age, gender, attitude, motivation, goals of language learning, learning preference, aptitude, national origin, language teaching method, task requirement, teachers’ expectation, cultural distinctions, language-related beliefs, and linguistic proficiency (Su, 2018; Rubin, 1987; Chamot & Kupper, 1989; Oxford, 1989; Oxford & Nyikos, 1989; Abraham & Vann, 1987; Bialystok, 1979).

The present study intends to focus on the factors of language learning strategy patterns and learner gender in the context of Afghanistan. It is reported that learner gender as a social factor affects LLS choice and employment. Generally, research in the field suggests that female language learners apply different strategies than their male counterparts. These studies claimed that females use strategies more than males (Oxford, 1989). As a case in point, Politzer (1983) showed that female language learners apply social language learning strategies more frequently than males. Another study by Tabeti (2019) revealed that female language learners use memory, cognitive, metacognitive, and affective language learning strategies more frequently than males do. Overall, a large number of studies have been conducted in the EFL/ESL context investigating different variables (e.g., course level, gender, motivation, language being learned, course duration, and degree of awareness).

According to Riazi and Rahimi (2005), a wide range of studies have been conducted in the field of EFL/ESL, and most of these studies have sought South Asian language learners who possess their specific cultural backgrounds. Most of these studies have investigated the frequency and types of LLS that distinguish them from other Asian language learners. I believe the field still requires further research, including under-researched contexts among Asian countries, especially countries like Afghanistan, where few studies have been conducted to identify LLS patterns and use. In Afghanistan, English is offered as a school subject by the Ministry of Education, and the learners begin to learn English from the fourth grade in public schools. Presently,

English is the medium of teaching in some private schools in Afghanistan and is becoming the medium of instruction in some universities. Studies of LLS in this context can help teachers and instructors obtain insights regarding how Afghan EFL learners approach English language learning.

Accordingly, the present study intends to investigate the frequency patterns of LLS of Afghan EFL learners. It also aims to determine the effect of language learner gender on the use of learning strategies by Afghan learners majoring in English literature.

Literature Review

Naiman et al. (1978) conducted the first studies on language learning strategies (LLS). Their studies concluded that students with higher language proficiency used more LLS than those with lower language proficiency levels. Afterwards, using LLS became vital in language learning and teaching (Ruba, Habiba, Amir, Aslam, & Kiran, 2014).

Unlike in the past, when it was assumed that LLS were only influenced by language proficiency, several studies have shown that LLS could also be impacted by nationality, gender, aptitude, age, and culture (Riazi & Rahimi, 2005). Accordingly, the authors of this study provided some research on the LLS in the following paragraphs. Most of the studies have utilized SILL to determine LLS use. According to Oxford (1990), a mean of 2.4 and lower has been suggested for “low”, a mean range of 2.5-3.4 for “medium,” and a mean range of 3.5-5 for “high” levels of strategy use. The researchers below have applied the same criteria for classifying their participants, as suggested by Oxford (1990), while working in different cultural contexts.

Park (1997) researched students of two Korean universities and used the LLS self-reporting questionnaire (SILL, ESL/EFL 7.0 Student Version), devised by Oxford (1990). He found out that the relationship between LLS and L2 proficiency was linear. Moreover, students of the target universities were moderate LLS users, using metacognitive strategies the most, followed by compensation, memory, cognitive, social, and affective strategies.

Bremner (1999) has conducted research similar to Park (1997). His research on City University of Hong Kong students found that compensation strategies were used the most, followed by metacognitive, cognitive, social, memory, and affective strategies. In conclusion, he maintained that Hong Kong EFL learners were medium LLS users.

Another study was conducted by Wharton (2000) on multicultural university students in Singapore who were learning Japanese and French as a foreign language. According to him, Singapore EFL learners were moderate strategy users in language learning. Their LLS use indicated social strategies the most frequent, while affective strategies were the least frequent. The author claimed that more proficient learners use more LLS than less proficient students, and male students use more strategies than females.

A group of researchers has evaluated Iranian students in terms of LLS use (Riazi & Rahimi, 2005; Kamalizad & Khalilzadeh, 2016; Salahshoura, Sharifib, & Salahshour, 2013). They concluded that metacognitive strategies are the most frequently used strategy and that Iranian students are medium-level LLS users, differing from the other strategies in terms of their orders.

Similar to the study conducted by Iranian researchers, metacognitive and social strategies were found to be the most frequent among Malaysian students (Naidu & Kumar, 2018, p. 76). The authors also found several similarities regarding the use of

LLS among male and female students. However, Salahshour Sharifib, and Salahshour (2013) maintained that female Iranian language learners used more strategies than their male counterparts.

Another study conducted by Mahmud and Nur (2018) in Makassar, Indonesia, surveyed gender differences and concluded that cognitive, compensation, and affective strategies were the most frequently used strategies by female learners, while male students mostly used memory, metacognitive, and social strategies. Erdogan and Ozdemir (2018) also found that students' gender and field of study have influenced the selection of language approach and the use of language learning strategy.

Balcı and Üğüten (2018) maintained that metacognitive strategies were used to the greatest extent, while cognitive strategies were used least commonly among students at a Turkish university. Meanwhile, they did not notice any difference between male and female learners concerning LLS use, except for the memory strategy.

Daflizar, Sulistiyo, and Kamil (2022) asserted that Indonesian EFL learners utilize metacognitive strategies at a high level. However, they apply other LLSs, such as memory, cognitive, social, compensation, and affective strategies, at a medium level.

Alhaisoni (2012) found that students in a Saudi university used language learning strategies from low to medium levels. The author further discussed that cognitive and metacognitive strategies were used the most, whereas affective and memory strategies were used the least. He also reported statistically significant results connected to the gender of the students. Although male and female students did not differ in employing other strategies, female students used social strategies more commonly than their male counterparts, and overall, they also implemented LLSs more than male students. The Author also found that highly proficient students used language learning strategies more than low-proficiency students.

Some researchers have studied the relation between LLS use and one or more other variants. For instance, Balcı (2017) found that learning styles also impacted LLSs. Chang and Liu (2013) found that students with higher English proficiency levels used language strategies more than those with lower proficiency levels. They also interpreted that the first group used metacognitive strategies the most, while the second group used compensation strategies the most. Moreover, Mohammadipour, Rashid, Rafik-Galea, and Thai (2018) found that students with more positive emotions used more language learning strategies. Finally, Guapacha Chamorro and Benavidez Paz (2017) improved students' LLSs by implementing explicit strategy instruction, a cognitive academic language learning approach, and task-based language teaching.

Overall, the findings of the studies indicated that LLS use could be impacted by cultural background, gender, and some other factors. To the best of the researchers' knowledge, no study has been conducted in Afghanistan regarding the use of LLSs. Therefore, the present study aims to investigate the relationship between patterns of LLS use of Afghan EFL learners in the light of learner gender preferences.

Research Questions

The present study aims to answer the following three questions:

1. What patterns of language learning strategies do Afghan EFL learners use?
2. What are the most and the least frequent language learning strategies among Afghan EFL learners?

3. Is there any significant difference between Afghan male and female EFL learners in terms of using language learning strategies?

Research Methodology

Participants

The sample population in this study contains 140 English language and literature students from Parwan University (PU) of Afghanistan. Their ages ranged from 18 to 25 years old. They were selected based on a convenience sampling procedure. Of the sample, 70 were males, and 70 were females. All the participants spoke Persian-Dari or Pashto as their first language and learned English as a foreign language.

Instruments

Two instruments, a demographic questionnaire and the Oxford Strategy Inventory for Language Learning (SILL) (Version 7.0, 50-item for ESL/EFL), were used in the present study. The demographic questionnaire was used as an instrument to elicit the basic information (e.g., age, gender, university year, and the duration they have been learning the target language).

To measure the frequency, pattern, and level of learners' strategy use, the self-report Strategy Inventory for Language Learning (SILL) devised by Oxford (1990, pp. 293-300) was administered. The mentioned self-report questionnaire contains six categories: compensation, metacognitive, cognitive, memory, social, and affective strategies, which include 50 items with five Likert-scale choices: "1: never or almost never true of me" to "5: always or almost always true of me." The questionnaire was pilot-tested with the EFL participants majoring in the English language and literature. To compute the reliability of the questionnaire, the pilot results were analyzed using SPSS. To ensure the internal consistency of the questionnaire, the Cronbach alpha coefficient was calculated. The reliability turned out to be 0.856, which was considered high.

Data Collection Procedure

After preparing and printing the questionnaires, the researchers gained consent from the head of the English department at Parwan University and arranged the time for conducting the research.

The demographic questionnaire, along with the SILL (V7.0 EFL/ESL) questionnaire, was given to English-majoring students. They were first assigned to respond to the demographic questionnaire, and also told that writing their names was optional. Later on, they were required to fill out the SILL questionnaire rating on a five-point Likert scale about the strategies they actually employ in learning the English language, rather than the ones they wish to apply. Learners were informed that there is no wrong or right answer and they ought to choose simply one of the five numbers based on how they learn English, and also they were told that their participation is voluntary; there is no credit/discredit for taking part in this study, and their identities are kept confidential. Moreover, the students were allowed to ask if they had any questions or problems regarding the demography or SILL questionnaire. Most of them had no difficulties in understanding and answering the questionnaires. If any clarification were necessary, the researcher and English instructors would provide a Persian translation. The total data collection procedure took one hour.

Data Analysis Procedure

After data collection, all background forms and SILL questionnaires were reviewed, and incomplete demography forms or questionnaires were discarded. Among English majoring classes, 140 (70 males and 70 females) completed demographic questionnaires, and SILLs were considered as valid data and coded for statistical analysis to determine the learners' LLS use within the study. Cronbach's alpha was computed to check the internal consistency reliability of the questionnaire. Also, the data were analyzed using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) to reveal descriptive statistics (e.g., frequency, percentage, mean, and standard deviation) of the LLSs used by the target learners. Moreover, an independent T-test procedure was conducted to compare the mean differences between males and females in terms of LLS preference and use.

Results

Reliability of SILL Questionnaire

There were 50 items in the SILL, and a five-point Likert-scale questionnaire was designed. To calculate the reliability of the questionnaire, Cronbach's alpha was conducted in SPSS, and the SILL questionnaire was revealed to be reliable in the Afghan context. The result of Cronbach's alpha is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Cronbach's Alpha for Reliability of Questionnaire

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
0.856	50

Based on the analysis result of Cronbach's alpha for the reliability of the SILL questionnaire, the coefficient alpha of the questionnaire was 0.856 ($\alpha > 0.750$), which means all items in the questionnaire were reliable to be applied in the Afghanistan context.

Overall Language Learning Strategies Use

To answer the first and second research questions, which seek to identify the patterns and frequency of language learning strategies used by Afghan EFL learners, the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) was utilized to calculate the mean and standard deviation of the six LLS categories. Table 2 presents the overall strategy use, mean scores, standard deviations, and rank order of Afghan EFL language learners.

Table 2. Mean scores of language Learning Strategies Use

Category	Mean	Std. Dev.	Rank
Memory Strategies	3.05	0.16	6
Cognitive Strategies	3.13	0.09	5
Compensation Strategies	3.35	0.14	1
Metacognitive Strategies	3.34	0.07	2
Affective Strategies	3.20	0.07	4
Social Strategies	3.33	0.05	3
Overall LLS Use	3.23	0.48	

Based on the frequency analysis of the data shown in Table 2, the total mean score for overall language learning strategies was 3.23, indicating that Afghanistan EFL learners are medium strategy users. According to the results shown in Table 2, the most frequently used strategies with high rankings were compensation strategies (M = 3.35), followed by metacognitive strategies (M = 3.34), and social strategies (M = 3.33). Meanwhile, the least favored strategies by Afghan EFL learners were affective strategies (M = 3.20), cognitive strategies (M = 3.13), and memory strategies (M = 3.05), respectively.

Gender Influence on Language Learning Strategy Use

To answer the third research question, which investigates the difference between male and female language learners in terms of overall LLS use and its six categories, the independent sample T-test was applied. Table 3 below reports the mean scores, standard deviations, and the level of language learning strategy use in relation to the impact of gender on the learners' LLS choice and employment.

Table 3. Mean Differences between Males and Females in the Use of LLS

Category	N	Gender	Mean	Std. Dev.	Sig.
Memory	70	Male	3.14	0.55	0.11
	70	Female	2.97	0.65	
Cognitive	70	Male	3.26	0.60	0.01
	70	Female	3.00	0.59	
Compensation	70	Male	3.42	0.76	0.33
	70	Female	3.29	0.82	
Metacognitive	70	Male	3.37	0.68	0.56
	70	Female	3.31	0.68	
Affective	70	Male	3.22	0.73	0.77
	70	Female	3.19	0.72	
Social	70	Male	3.39	0.62	0.42
	70	Female	3.29	0.74	
Overall LLS Use of Gender	70	Male	3.29	0.46	0.08
	70	Female	3.16	0.44	

Note: The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level

The results of the T-test in Table 3 indicated that there was no significant difference between male and female language learners in terms of overall language learning strategies use and employment. As Table 3 shows, male language learners outperformed (M=3.29) females (M=3.16) in the total average of LLS use, but no significant difference between males and females ($P > 0.08$) was indicated in terms of overall language learning strategies use.

Furthermore, according to Table 3, male language learners outnumbered in all six strategy categories. For example, the mean score for memory strategies of male language learners was (M=3.14), while the mean for female language learners was (M=2.97), the mean score of cognitive strategies for males was (M=3.26) and for females was (M=3.00), the mean score of compensation strategies for males was (M=3.40) and for female was (M3.29). Similarly, the mean score for metacognitive

strategies of males was ($M=3.37$) while for females was ($M=3.31$), the mean score of males for affective strategies was (3.22) and for females was ($M=3.19$). Finally, the mean scores for males' social strategies were ($M=3.39$) and for females were ($M=3.29$).

Although based on mean differences, male language learners outperformed females across all six categories of language learning strategies, there was no statistically significant difference in the five strategy categories. The only category that showed a significant difference was cognitive strategies ($P < 0.01$).

Discussion

Overall Language Learning Strategy Use

From the outset, the answer to the first two research questions could be extracted from Table 2. What patterns of language learning strategies do Afghan EFL learners use? And what are the most and least frequent language learning strategies among Afghan EFL learners? As per Table 2, the mean for overall language learning strategy use among Afghan EFL learners was ($M= 3.23$), indicating that Afghan EFL learners are moderate strategy users. Afghan EFL learners used compensation strategies ($M = 3.35$) and metacognitive strategies ($M = 3.34$) the most, followed by social strategies ($M = 3.33$) and affective strategies ($M = 3.20$). The least frequently used strategies among Afghan EFL learners were cognitive strategies ($M = 3.13$) and memory strategies ($M = 3.05$).

The research showed that Afghan EFL learners were somewhat similar to other Asian EFL learners in terms of strategy use (Chang, 2013; Peacock & Ho, 2003; Wharton, 2000; Bremner, 1999; Park, 1997; Oh, 1992). For instance, Asian students, including Afghans, are moderate LLS users, and they favor compensation and metacognitive strategies the most. It is also worth mentioning that memory strategies are the least favored strategy.

Having said that, compensation strategies are commonly used by Asian students because they help them think critically and cope with the language limitations while speaking or writing. According to Oxford (1990), these strategies enable learners to extract meaning from the linguistic limitations, use gestures, mime, ask for help, and even switch between their mother tongue and L2 or even avoid communication partially or completely. A high level of compensation strategy use has a root in the low proficiency of learners in the target language. Afghans often use compensation strategies due to lower English proficiency. The reason behind their limited proficiency in English could be a lack of opportunities to use English outside the classroom.

Moreover, the findings of this research do not comply with the results of other studies conducted in the Asian context (e.g., Nikoopour et al., 2011; Riazi & Rahimi, 2005; Park, 1997; Oh, 1992; Green, 1991), whose findings revealed that Asian EFL learners were moderate users in terms of using compensation strategies.

Metacognitive strategies were ranked second most frequent among Afghan EFL learners. These strategies were also favored by some other Asian countries (Tabeti, 2019; Ho & Ng, 2016; Radwan, 2011; Aliakbari & Hayatzadeh, 2008; Riazi & Rahimi, 2005; Park, 1997; Oh, 1992). The high frequency of metacognitive strategy use among Asian countries may be described by the lack of natural settings for using the target language.

Another reason is linked to the teaching culture. Since explicit language teaching is the dominant method in Afghanistan, language learners are always expected to learn language through explicit rules. It is not unusual for learners to acquire conscious skills or behaviors (metacognitive strategies) to learn the English language.

According to Table 2, Afghan EFL learners are moderate users of social strategy. However, this result is inconsistent with the findings of some previous studies (O'Malley & Chamot, 1990; Politzer & McGroarty, 1985). The studies claimed that Asian language learners preferred Rote Learning and rule-based learning instead of communicative approaches. On the contrary, the results of this study showed that Afghan EFL learners were also inclined to engage in social interactions to learn English as a foreign language.

Another significant finding of this study is that Afghan EFL learners use memory strategies less frequently. These results align with some previous studies in the Asian context (e.g., Tabeti, 2019; Ho & Ng, 2016; Peacock & Ho, 2003; Oh, 1992). Asian language learners, including Afghan learners, rarely report memory strategies. In other words, they may not be aware of how often they use and employ memory strategies in the process of language learning (Kamalizad & Kalilzadeh, 2016; Oxford, 1990).

Relationship of Learner Gender and LLS Use

To answer the third research question (Is there any significant difference between male and female Afghan EFL learners in terms of using language learning strategies?), Table 3 suggests some differences between male and female learners regarding all six language learning strategies and their overall usage. The study revealed that both male and female Afghan EFL learners were medium strategy users. However, male EFL learners' means outnumbered those of their female counterparts in overall language learning strategy use; no significant differences were found between male and female learners in any of the six strategies, except for the cognitive strategies.

The findings of this research contradict several studies conducted in the first half of the 20th century (e.g., Khalil, 2005; Ok, 2003; Oxford & Ehrman, 1995; Oxford, 1990), which found that female language learners used more strategies than males. However, the results of this study comply with the findings of some recent studies. For example, Yilmaz (2010), Marina (2017), and Tabeti (2019) also found that there is no significant difference between male and female learners in terms of overall language learning strategy use. Moreover, this study's results align with Radwan (2011), who reported that males outperformed female language learners.

Conclusion

This study intended to investigate the overall patterns of language learning strategy use and learner gender of English language and literature learners at Parwan University, Parwan, Afghanistan. The results of the present study demonstrated that, irrespective of gender, Afghanistan EFL learners adopted all language learning strategies, but with different categories and frequency rates. Moreover, the findings of this study revealed that Afghan EFL learners were average users of language learning strategies; compensation and metacognitive strategies were the most frequently used strategies. In contrast, memory and cognitive strategies emerged as the least preferred strategies among Afghan language learners. In addition, memory and cognitive strategies were used in between. Furthermore, the results of the T-test showed that there was no significant difference in overall language learning strategy use between male and female

language learners in terms of overall strategy use and five strategy categories, except for the cognitive strategies.

The findings of this research suggest several implications for classrooms, teachers, and English syllabus developers in Afghanistan. According to the findings of this study, Afghan EFL learners are moderate strategy users, suggesting that they may not be aware of all available strategies of English language learning. The first and most important implication of this study is to provide Afghan EFL learners with opportunities to practice and be aware of language learning strategies. English language instructors can help EFL learners practice direct and indirect language learning strategies either consciously or unconsciously during English classes in schools or universities. Moreover, frequent use of metacognitive and compensatory behaviors is an indication of explicit and rule-based language syllabi and course designs. Hence, attempts should also have been made to design and develop syllabuses that maintain the balance in conscious and unconscious learning strategies. Finally, language learning materials, syllabi, and curricula should be designed in a way that activities and tasks are diversified to cover all language learners with various characteristics, styles, and strategy preferences. Unlike some factors, language learning strategies are teachable. Afghan EFL teachers should design their activities around these factors to assist their learners to learn more easily, quickly, and effectively. Moreover, it helps language learners keep learning even if they are outside the classroom (Oxford & Crookall, 1989).

Conflicts of Interest

The authors certify that they have no affiliations with or involvement in any organization or entity with any financial interest (such as honoraria; educational grants; participation in speakers' bureaus; membership, employment, consultancies, stock ownership, or other equity interest; and expert testimony or patent-licensing arrangements), or non-financial interest (such as personal or professional relationships, affiliations, knowledge or beliefs) in the subject matter or materials discussed in this manuscript.

Ethical Approval and Consent to Participate

This study was conducted through a logical procedure. The participants were convinced to take part in this study after the researchers obtained their permission by writing a consent letter to them. They confirmed their willingness by signing the consent letter before they participated. Those who were not satisfied are excluded from this study.

Consent for Publication

All participants included in this research study are satisfied with publishing their declarations either online or in the press. Their permissions were also obtained through a consent letter.

Availability of Supporting Data

The data that support the findings of this study are available on request from the corresponding author. The data are not publicly available due to privacy or ethical considerations.

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